

INTEGRATIVE APPROACHES IN CONDUCTING LITERACY CLASSES TO BRING OUT THE CREATIVE ABILITIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the integrated approaches in conducting literacy lessons to bring out the creative abilities of primary school students.*

Keywords: *primary school students, creative ability, conducting literacy classes, integrated approach.*

Particular attention was paid to the fact that one of the important factors influencing the methods and means of developing the creative abilities of primary school students is the cooperation between the teacher and the student. It is known that the educational process has a reciprocal character and consists of equal relations between the teacher and the students. The teacher who leads this process is responsible for the correct organization of the educational process, the correct implementation of educational goals and educational results. However, this cannot be the basis for the false idea that the educational process takes place under the complete control of the teacher. The requirement of modern times is to achieve a positive result with the help of a cooperative relationship, not by subjugating someone. It should not be forgotten that the design of students' activities in the educational process is not only a mechanism for assimilating the basics of science, but is also aimed at the development of general social and cultural skills of the individual. In our opinion, the educational situation is a variable system that organizes the educational process, and it consists of two parts:

- Cooperation between students and teachers;

- cooperation of students among themselves. The cooperation of students with the teacher begins with the teacher's help to the students. It gradually becomes active and turns into learning activities. As a result, the relationship between the teacher and the students moves to a cooperative position. The analysis of materials shows that the acquisition of knowledge is productive only when logical tasks are performed cooperatively. In scientific sources, it is customary to call such an organization of education a situation of productive activity in cooperation. After analyzing the pedagogical literature and the results of our creative experience, it is appropriate to point out two main principles of organizing a situation of productive educational activities in cooperation:

1. The principle of consistency of content in education. According to it, when a person organizes his activity on the basis of a specific goal, the continuous formation of this activity is felt.

2. The principle of the connection between teacher-student cooperation and independent creative activity. Cooperation with students in the educational process is of great importance. The extent to which students devote themselves to learning depends on the teacher's ability to build this partnership. The correct organization of the environment in the educational activities of the teacher and students increases students' interest in science and encourages them to use all their energy and enthusiasm. This is a form of interaction in which the student sees himself not as an

object of pedagogical education, but as an independent and freely acting person. The teacher's approach to students, as if asking for help, while clarifying some information on the topic under study, deepens the cooperation activity. The transformation of students into learners and trainees is not only a condition for a successful teaching and learning process, but also an important condition for their upbringing as versatile people in all respects. The student becomes a person who receives knowledge and education in the process of education and upbringing. Sh.A. Amonashvili emphasizes the need to build a cooperative relationship with the student in the educational process and says: “ This is regulated by the manner of behavior of the educator in the educational process.”

In an atmosphere of love, trust, cooperation and respect, the student learns the tasks easily. Since his achievements, independent thinking and creative research are highly valued, the student begins to strive to complete more complex educational tasks. The thinker considers decency to be the most important criterion of morality. Politeness and morality help a person to gain a certain status and respect among the people around him. While showing the human role of manners, Alisher Navoi expresses the following thoughts: “Manners deserve the blessing of the elders and they will enjoy the blessing of the elders for life. It puts love in one's heart forever. It makes the young people look great. People know how to behave and avoid humiliation. It puts one's nature on the path of humanity and gives peace of mind to one's client. You will see that it is good for the little ones and enough for the adults. Adab and humility shine the mirror of friendship, bring light from both sides. Bowing and respect are enough for those who are humble and polite, and he reaps this precious harvest. These qualities are the beginning of good morals in people's behavior, and when this quality is firmly established, it is possible for love to become halal. If there is good behavior on both sides, respect will appear in exchange for politeness and modesty”. In Alisher Navoi's interpretation, politeness, which is the basis of good behavior, is considered the most important link of all human qualities. The thinker emphasizes that positive qualities such as kindness, patience, modesty, love, loyalty, generosity and hilm (gentleness) manifest themselves only in the form of polite and moral people. He continues his reflections on spiritual and moral qualities by giving each of them a complete definition. This creates a basis for regulating this relationship, as well as for a person to fully understand his social duties and develop a sense of responsibility for fulfilling them. The establishment of consistent, systematic, continuous and goal-oriented education promotes their active participation in the process of social relations of various directions and content, as well as their self-education. In the formation of the worldview of the young generation, it is important for them to master the basics of natural, social and human sciences taught in educational institutions. The spiritual and moral image of a person, his approaches to life, the essence of the values and moral principles that are of paramount importance to him constitute the content of his worldview. The enrichment of the worldview, in turn, ensures a gradual stabilization of the personal properties and qualities of a person. A worldview that expresses good ideas in its content helps to enrich the positive qualities that are manifested in the image of a person. By its nature, the worldview is differentiated into a scientific (with a certain philosophical system) and a simple (without a certain philosophical system) type of worldview.

On the basis of the scientific worldview, there are ideas that have gained stability as a result of continuous and consistent assimilation of the foundations of existing sciences and active participation in the process of social relations. The formation of a person's worldview is a complex process of a long-term, dynamic nature. The main signs and essence of intellectual education and

scientific worldview. Intellectual education plays an important role in the formation of a person's worldview. Intellectual education is an educational activity aimed at giving a person knowledge about the nature and development of society, forming his mental (cognitive) abilities and thinking, and forming a worldview on the basis of their effective implementation. Today in the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the intellectual education of young people. In accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education”, adopted at the IX Congress of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 1997, the resolution adopted at the XII Session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the “National Program for Personnel Training”, highly qualified personnel who meet high moral and ethical requirements are trained. It is emphasized that education is one of the priorities of state policy. In order to become highly qualified personnel who meet high moral and ethical requirements, one must thoroughly assimilate the existing scientific and professional knowledge. Therefore, deep knowledge makes it possible to understand the essence of natural and social processes, to identify and evaluate their positive and negative aspects, to introduce them and create a basis for the development of creative, free and independent thinking skills in them. Education is a cooperative activity of the teacher and students, and in this process the development of the individual, his education and upbringing is also realized. In the classroom, the teacher conveys his knowledge, skills and abilities to students through exercises, and students acquire the ability to apply them by mastering them. In the learning process, students use different forms of learning, that is, they rely on specific differences in receiving, processing and applying the learned information. In the course of education, the problems of education and upbringing are solved in the form of cooperation between teachers and students during lessons, independent work of students and extracurricular activities. The purpose of education is determined in accordance with the needs of society. Therefore, the goal of education should be appropriate and proportionate. The goal of education in scientific literature is to create skills and competencies, develop logical-creative thinking, improve communicative competence, instill national thought, form oriental education and define personality. It is emphasized that this is spiritual enrichment. Based on the goal of education, the communication culture of students is improved by increasing their independent thinking, oral and written competence and developing their logical thinking. Based on the goal of education, spiritual, ideological and sophisticated education is provided. In the process of learning languages, there is an opportunity to get closer to the cultural and moral values of people. It would not be a mistake to say that there was a change that lasted for several hundred years.

This shows that our President cares about our future, our future generation and thinks that “all the children of our country are my children, they should be stronger, more educated and certainly happier than us,” and that there is a wise policy behind this. It is known that the introduction of progressive pedagogy and new information technologies in education not only increases the effectiveness of training, but is also important for the formation of an independent and logically thinking, versatile and highly moral person through the application of the achievements of science in practice. Today, interest in the use of interactive methods and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. One of the reasons for this is that previously in traditional education, students were only taught to assimilate ready-made knowledge, while the use of modern technologies allows them to search for the acquired knowledge, learn and think independently, analyze and even draw their own conclusions. In this

process, the teacher creates conditions for personal development, education, learning and upbringing, while performing the functions of management and guidance.

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